

TEACHING DESIGN AND EMOTION IN THE FOUNDATION YEAR: AN INDUSTRIAL DESIGN APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This paper showcases two design tools; the 'storyboard' and 'a day in the life' demonstrated to design students in their foundational year (first year) of study. By employing these tools during the design process the aim was to provoke students to consider and design for emotional experiences for potential users. The assessment asked students to design an MP3 player using these tools. This is demonstrated through a student project that successfully used the tools and method introduced. The teaching theory, project context, student outcome as well as challenges faced by students using this approach are discussed. The paper concludes with implications for teaching emotion theory at an undergraduate level and potential future directions.

Keywords: Industrial Design Education, Teaching Design and Emotion.

INTRODUCTION

There is an abundance of design and emotion research (Hassenzahl, 2010; Desmet, 2002; Hekkert, 2002) as well as various tools and methods for designing for emotional experiences from an industry perspective (Kujala, Roto, Väänänen-Vainio-Mattila, Karapanos and Sinnelä, 2011; Desmet, Overbeeke & Tax, 2001). This paper explores the questions: how

do design educators incorporate this valid new knowledge on emotion design? And, how can we educate designers to employ emotional aspects of interaction in design projects? There appears to be limited available literature pertaining to emotion design education for Industrial Design students, especially at the foundational level of study. McDonagh-Philp and Lebbon (2000) outline the use of mood boards and action research as potentially tools in an Industrial Design course. Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Hummels, & Wensveen (2002) presented masters projects that focused on designing for beauty in use. Likewise, Eggink & van der Bijl-Brouwer (2010) asked a second year Industrial Engineering cohort to consider emotional aspects during a series of workshops. In this paper the unit titled Product Usability, in which design and emotion theory is taught at Queensland University of Technology to first year Industrial Design students, is presented. The unit aims to introduce students to foundational knowledge of human factors, ergonomics and emotion theory and tools. The paper presents the design process from a student project that successfully utilised the tools and methods provided, and outlines benefits and challenges faced from a student perspective. It concludes with implications for teaching design and emotion and potential future directions.

Figure 1. Product Interaction Timeline (Wrigley, Gomez & Popovic, 2010)

TEACHING DESIGN EMOTION THEORY

An understanding of physical, cognitive and emotional needs of people is vital to the development of usable artifacts. The unit provides the knowledge as the basis for a user-centred design philosophy. The teaching theory delivered through the 13-week semester includes basic user-centred design and ergonomics principles as well as an introduction to emotions. Norman's (2004) three levels of cognition; visceral, behavioural and reflective were presented. The Product Interaction Timeline was also introduced (Figure 1), which is used to contextualise the idea that emotional experiences need to be considered before, during and after user-product interaction. This helped students focus on thinking beyond merely product attributes to a more holistic experience of interaction. Two tools were introduced including Storyboards and A day in the life. Storyboards assist to bring stories and meaningful analysis of the user experiences into the design process while A day in the life allows to consider thoughts, feelings and actions when interacting with a product or service in context

(Stickdorn and Schneider, 2010). These tools help to capture user experiences in a simple but meaningful way for undergraduate design students.

PROJECT CONTEXT

The project involves the design of a portable music player. Initially the project requires students to test existing portable music players in small groups. Students are then asked to design a portable music player individually. Students were provided with six scenarios to design for. Scenario 1 is design a portable music player for elderly aged 60+; Scenario 2 is for one-handed use; Scenario 3 involves designing for beginner or professional cyclists; Scenario 4 invites students to design an aftermarket music player for the automotive market; Scenario 5 is to design for children; and Scenario 6 to design for young adults for socialising and enjoyment purposes.

STUDENT OUTCOMES

Following are images from a student whose project successfully utilised both tools in the design process.

Figure 2. Student representation of A day in the life of for elderly aged 60+.

The student chose to design for a portable music player for the elderly aged 60+ (scenario 1).

A day in the life

Figure 2 exemplifies the student’s version of a day in the life of elderly users. It shows some of the initial thinking around the user groups’ daily activities including exercising, cycling and gardening and consideration of visibility, hearing and memory loss. The tool assisted in drawing out deeper issues including aspects of socialisation, contemplation, relationships and friendships.

Storyboard

Figure 3 illustrates the student representation of the storyboard. It shows a portable music player specifically designed to fit into the users’ daily activities and demonstrates the user interacting with it while gardening, one of the activities identified through A day in the life. The storyboard permitted the student to identify further critical insights of user needs, wants and requirements as the notes in the storyboard indicate:

“From observation/user feedback, during the process of gardening, you wouldn’t be interacting much with the device unless required, i.e. stopping or volume adjust.”

“...strapping device on upper arm, user said it feels better.”

“Interacting with the device during context, doesn’t intrude with the user’s accessibility.”

Further since the storyboard was conducted using a prototype of the intended design the student could also evaluate aspects of the design impacting on the usability and enjoyment. For instance:

“Buttons are large... to accommodate glove users.”

“Suggestion to include audible tunes, vibration or confirmation message for better feedback.”

In this instance the student also conducted blank-model prototyping, based on the feedback from the Storyboard and A day in the life tool. The final outcome combined all of these aspects regarding product use and interaction in context. Figure 4 illustrates the presentation board outlining the way the product is potentially used from initial set-up, during use and after use. This links in with the interaction

Figure 3. Student representation of Storyboard for elderly aged 60+.

timeline initially presented (Figure 1).

It is argued that within the context of first year the analysis performed here shows a successful application and analysis of A day in the life and Storyboard tools to identify aspects regarding the use of the product in context over time. The use of these tools, alongside theory, facilitates students to consider more appropriate and enjoyable concepts and designs based on user needs, wants and requirements.

STUDENT FEEDBACK

Students were asked to retrospectively provide feedback regarding the content. The purpose was to ascertain whether students found the approach and tools useful for exploring emotional aspects of design. Students were asked how valuable they thought the content of design and emotion provided was and how the design tools assisted them in the design process. Two responses include:

"...[the tools] helped me especially with regard to how I could bring out the problems associated with the context

through using a storyboard. The categorisation of emotions into the three levels... also helped me better understand the concept of emotion in design and hence understanding the emotional requirements of the context of the project."

"In terms of the content on design and emotion, it was a very valuable lesson; it assisted me to understand my design project within the context in much more depth as well as understanding human behaviour."

These comments indicate that students perceived the teaching tools as useful in designing for emotional experiences. They were also asked how they considered the final design outcomes in regards to emotions. One student stated:

"I think I have achieved only the short-term goal in making my design less frustrating to use. In the long-run I definitely feel that more could be done to prolong the positive experience of the user when using the product."

This suggests that even though the tools were useful they felt there was room for improvement when it comes to designing for emotional experiences. From an educational perspective it is positive to see that students recognised there was still a long way to go to

Figure 4. Final presentation board showing interaction with product before, during and after use.

design for emotional experiences. Students were also asked about the challenges they faced incorporating emotional aspects into their design:

“The main challenge is to recognize the user or user group... different users may differ in their emotional needs, narrowing down to a specific user group especially in terms of age helped a lot in the design. Researching the user and understanding their emotional needs was also quite challenging.”

“The main challenges of incorporating emotional aspects were understanding the chosen context and audience. Recording down the possible outcomes with constant testing, finding flaws and errors... There is just too much to find out... due to the sophistication of emotional aspects of the relationship between human and product”.

Once more the statements from the students point to the fact that they understood the theory regarding the importance of designing for emotional experiences and recognised its complexity.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Product Usability is a unit taught in the foundation year of Industry Design and is used as a vehicle to educate students on human-factors and ergonomic principles focusing on physical, cognitive and emotional aspects of interaction. The unit educates students on current design emotion theory and contextualises this with the product interaction timeline. Further, students are presented with two tools including the Storyboard and A day in the life that promotes students to go deeper into the needs, wants and requirements to design for emotional experiences. It is important to note that this unit has been run by the first Author for the last 4 years and this year was the first time in conjunction with the second Author the tools were introduced as a means to translate the emotional design theoretical content into the design process.

The implications for design education of this approach to teaching design and emotion at the foundation level are encouraging. As the student project illustrates these tools, alongside other traditional techniques, appear to aid student thinking about emotional interactions. From initial consideration of user needs, contextualising user activities within A day in the life tool helped elicit more comprehensive analysis of user concerns. Further, combining this with Storyboards

allowed an even deeper awareness of emotional requirements. From the feedback provided it seems students understood the importance of going beyond basic needs to explore emotional aspects of interaction through designs. Although students acknowledged the need to design for emotional experiences, they could see there was a long way to go before the designs would target positive emotional experiences.

In future versions of this unit more time and focus will be catered to developing their designs in regards to emotional aspects of interaction. Another avenue could be to perhaps allow the students to focus solely on the emotional aspects of the interaction. However this approach poses other challenges as students might begin to decouple emotional concerns as separate from other critical aspects of interaction (physical and cognitive), which would work against the educational objectives. Finally it is hoped that this paper can instigate a more critical discussion around the diverse teaching approaches that exists to assist undergraduate students to design for emotional experiences.

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